

Teacher Trainers' Motivation in Transformation of Teaching and Learning: The Fun Way Approach

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Abstract—The purpose of the study is to investigate the level of intrinsic motivation of trainers after attending a Continuous Professional Development Course (CPD) organized by Institute of Teacher Training Malaysia titled, “Transformation of Teaching and Learning the Fun Way”. This study employed a survey whereby 96 teacher trainers were given Situational Intrinsic Motivational Scale (SIMS) Instruments. Confirmatory factor analysis was carried out to get the validity of this instrument in local setting. Data were analyzed with SPSS for descriptive statistic. Semi- structured interviews were also administrated to collect qualitative data on participants' experiences after participating in the two-day fun-filled program. The findings showed that the participants' level of intrinsic motivation showed higher mean than the amotivation. The results revealed that the intrinsic motivation mean is 19.0 followed by Identified regulation with a mean of 17.4, external regulation 9.7 and amotivation 6.9. The interview data also revealed that the participants were motivated after attending this training program. It can be concluded that this program, which was organized by Institute of Teacher Training Malaysia, was able to enhance participants' level of motivation. Self-Determination Theory (SDT) as a multidimensional approach to motivation was utilized. Therefore, teacher trainers may have more success using the “The fun way approach” in conducting training program in future.

Keywords—Teaching and Learning, Motivation, Teacher Trainer, SDT.

I. INTRODUCTION

REFLECTIVE practice can be a beneficial process in teacher professional development courses, both in pre-service and in-service teachers. Reflective practice can be considered as a platform where beginners in a discipline are able to recognize the connection between their own individual practices and those who have been successful. Reflective practices concepts involve well thought of practices while considering one's own experiences in applying knowledge while being coached by professionals. Many schools and departments of education and professional development programs adapted this concept [1]. As the concepts grew in popularity, some researchers continued to incorporate

reflective practices in their education program which focused on the process of reflective practices while sacrificing important content in teacher education [2]. Studies have proven that critical reflection upon experience can be an effective technique for professional development program [1].

Professional development programs need not always focus on specific teaching method and strategies; they can also focus on the teacher's attitude or motivation that affects the practice [3]. The ability to have a deeper understanding of their own teaching style, which will bring about a greater effectiveness as a teacher is one of the main advantage of reflective practice in professional development among educators. Other specific benefits pointed out include the validation and acknowledgement of an educator's ideals, positive and progressive challenges to tradition, the artistry of teaching, and applying theory to classroom practice through creativity and diversity.

Games were designed to utilize the knowledge and strategies of one game situation to enhance the learning and performance in another game situation without compromising on the subject matter that is being delivered [4]–[8]. One of the benefits of utilizing the fun way approach is by its connection with the games classification system. By utilizing the game, trainers were able to promote the transfer of previously learned information about one game situation to another new game learning by organizing the similarities and differences of the games [5], [6], [9]–[11]. These games situations allow for a richer understanding of the decisions made during games that promotes the transfer of previously learned information or skill and provides for a logical progression for tactical concepts to be presented. Besides that, by using this “fun way approach”, the subject matter, which is the main purpose of the games, is further enhanced. Trainers are also able to include elements of Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS), while planning some of the game situations to make the process of learning more meaningful and of higher quality.

Getting involved in games will offer a self-propelling motivation to participants [10]. Participation in games provides the type of motivation to learners that learning skills in isolation is often neglected and non-existent [10], [12]. The significance of enhancing motivation through strategies such as game play is recognized as a positive basis for learning experience [10], [13]. Trainers are able to use the motivation of games with the fun way approach to provide learning opportunities for participants to enhance the subject matter while fostering the task and skills of the games [10].

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Therefore, it is helpful for the trainer to simplify the game rules and strategies to develop the participants' understanding.

In this study, when participants were involved in a game, it can be explained that their self-determination as a cognitive understanding becoming deeper; there was an increase in behavior of participation in a game, which in turn improved their attitude. Motivational variable from Self-Determination Theory could predict participants' cognitive and affective experiences while going through game situations. Participants felt motivated by interest, enjoyment, satisfaction, and challenge of the activity by a deep sense of involvement [14]. Another researcher supported the statement that participants will be interested when they are successful in doing certain activities and will continue to participate [15]. Researchers have also suggested that more physical activity involvement pattern implies that participants are more attracted to physical activity overall [16], [17]. Therefore, the purpose of the study is to see whether participants using this fun way approach are motivated after the CPD course for two days. The term fun here implies to the fact that the participants actually enjoyed the subject matter being taught in a way that is enjoyable and conducive. It presents a platform, which makes the process of teaching and learning go up a level or two beyond the participants' capability, which in itself challenges the body and mind, hence making the effort itself just as rewarding. From an academic prospective, fun simply means engagement, doing and learning something that has meaning and purpose and yet challenging. When the fun element is present, engaging the students in participating the activities become much easier. Hands-on experiences will enhance learning and understanding. When students understand what they learn, they will remember the lesson taught, and this in turn can mold them into lifelong learners.

Self-Determination Theory [18] proposed that when participants move along the motivation continuum from lack of motivation toward intrinsic motivation, there will be an increase in understanding, increase in participation with a better attitude and outlook. Intrinsically motivated participants will be more likely to practice physically active behavior in the physical education environment and possibly become physically active on their own. SDT proposes that intrinsic motivation and autonomous types of extrinsic motivation (identified and integrated regulation) lead to positive cognitive, affective, and behavioral consequences [14], [19].

Research has demonstrated that enjoyment represents a key factor underlying the motivation for youth and participants to maintain positive engagement in physical activity [19]. In another study, it was reported that facilitating more enjoyable experiences may in turn have implication for motivation and continued participation even after completion of the program [20]. This fact is further substantiated that participants achieve higher levels of cognition, make connections and experience great moments when they are engaged yet motivated and show low level of stress. These learning outcomes just did not happen by chance but from careful planning which creates an atmosphere of radiant discovery, thus "the fun way approach" [21]. Therefore two-day fun-filled program titled

"Transformation of Teaching and Learning the Fun Way" was carefully planned for in-service teacher trainers.

II. METHOD

Mixed design of quantitative and qualitative method was adopted for this study. A survey was used to collect quantitative data and semi structured interview questions for qualitative technique. Survey method used was in the form of a questionnaire that could be administered to as many respondents [22]. In this study, the survey was carried out to gather information on the level of situation intrinsic motivation of teacher trainers in Malaysia after attending the CPD program. The Situational Intrinsic Motivational Scale (SIMS) instrument used in this research consists of 16 items. Each item is measured in Likert scale from 1 to 5 [23]. The Situation Intrinsic Motivation Scale inventory measures four subscales, namely intrinsic motivation domain (4 items), identified regulation domain (4 items), external regulation domain (4 items) and amotivation domain (4 items) [24]. Validity and the reliability of this SIMS instrument used are 0.82 to 0.88 [23], [24]. The questionnaire was given to two language experts and two physical education experts from the Faculty of Education, Teacher Training Institute for validation. The instrument was translated into the Malay Language via back-to-back translation. Cronbach Alpha value of .70 was reported in a study carried out in the Malaysian school setting [25]. Semi structured in-depth interview questions were developed for this study and used for each respondent but the questions remained open for additional questions that arose. When the respondents were probed for more information, they explained their experiences during their two days fun-filled experience. The interview data was audio taped, and hand written notes were taken too. To protect the participants' identity, pseudonyms and identification numbers were assigned and were used in data analyzed. The audios verbatim were transcribed in Microsoft Word 93. The data were then analyzed with Nvivo data analysis. Initial data management consisted of organizing the data, transcribing the interview, typing the transcription notes and making decision to analyze data by computer. The word transcription was uploaded as Source in Nvivo. The transcribed data in Source then coded for free notes and tree notes. All the free notes and tree noted further analyzed for categories.

III. RESULT

The findings from the survey, Table I showed that the participants' level of intrinsic motivation showed higher mean than the level of amotivation. The results revealed that the intrinsic motivation mean is 19.0 followed by identified regulation with a mean of 17.4, external regulation 9.7, and amotivation 6.9. The interview data from Table II also revealed that participants were motivated after attending this course. Table I showed participants' level of motivation after participating in a Transformation of Teaching and Learning the Fun Way Program.

TABLE I
 TEACHER TRAINERS' MOTIVATION IN CPD PROGRAM

	N	Mean	SD
Intrinsic Motivation	96	19.00	1.67
Identified Regulation	96	17.40	2.08
External Regulation	96	9.70	2.70
Amotivation	96	6.89	2.67
Valid N (listwise)	96		

Qualitative data from the interview were analyzed as shown in Table II. The data revealed a pattern, which showed the Transformation of Teaching and Learning: The Fun Way approach had shown some impact on participants' intrinsic motivation. Categories emerged from the qualitative data were pedagogical strategies, motivation and higher order thinking skills. Participants in this study described that these activities during Transformation of Teaching and Learning the Fun Way helped them to improve their pedagogical strategies. The participants were more motivated to use the fun activities in their future training program. Some of the participants also described that the games that were used in this training program were able to leave an impact on their students in training program by including higher order thinking skills (HOTS), where students will be able to create, analyze and solve game strategies in the activities. Participants also described that by providing strategic activities in games, it will create challenging experience for learners in problem solving situations related to their subject matter. The activities planned for the participant matches challenges with ability while focusing on the required task at hand. Participants were able to focus on the task at hand because the objectives and goals stated are clear and that they have a sense of control over their own actions.

TABLE II
 TREE NOTED FROM INTERVIEW DATA

Categories	Free Notes
Pedagogical Strategies	"Some techniques on how to apply the games in our class (A, L4) "I'm teaching English and I think we can practice in these kind of games and also divide them into different activities (B, L5) "I learned how to improve my method of teaching" (D, L5)
Motivation	"Making my teaching more fun at the same time and I can implement lots of things. I can enhance a attitude, and the most important thing I've learnt from here is if I'd like to have an impact to the knowledge among the fellow students, I can do it in various ways (D, L7)
Higher Order Thinking skills	Initially we've tried yet this one is quite challenging (A, L6) "I can now ask my students to create and analyze their sentences in a rather different and fun, yet challenging way (C, L4)

IV. DISCUSSION

It can be concluded from the findings, that the Transformation of Teaching and Learning Fun Way Program which was planned and organized by Institute of Teacher Training Malaysia was able to improve the participants' level of motivation. The Continuous Professional Development Course (CPD) can offer teachers and teacher trainer's opportunity to explore, develop management skills, and to reflect on their motivation and impact of ethical implication

towards the teaching profession [2], [3]. Based on subject matter, games that were designed and strategized for one game enhanced the learning and performance in another game situation [4]–[6], [8]. The study enhanced the Self Determination Theory that teacher trainers, who experienced motivation during the CPD course, may in turn have implication towards continued participation even after completion [20]. This study not only adds knowledge to Self Determination Theory but also add knowledge to teacher training practice. Therefore, teacher trainers may have more success using the "The fun way approach" in conducting training program in future.

V. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study is to investigate the level of intrinsic motivation of trainers after attending a Continuous Professional Development Course (CPD) titled, "Transformation of Teaching and Learning: The Fun Way Approach". It can be concluded that this program, which was organized by Institute of Teacher Training Malaysia, was able to enhance participants' level of motivation. Self-Determination Theory (SDT) as a multidimensional approach to motivation was utilized. From a learners perspective, "the fun way approach" which presents a learning environment which is comfortable, relaxed yet challenging has proven to be a likely strategy because learners are likely to remember and understand what they have learnt because of their direct involvement in solving the problem [21], [26]. This study also adds knowledge to Self Determination Theory, as participants are more likely to be engaged in behavior when they are self-determined. Besides that, the presence of the elements of HOTS in the process makes the art of learning more purposeful. Moreover the pedagogical perspective of a trainer, by including the "fun way approach, the process of learning goes up a level or two beyond the participants' capability because this presents a platform which challenges the body and mind hence making the effort itself as rewarding. The experience generated through this approach might not only meet the stipulated teaching objectives but also perhaps exceed it. Besides that, added elements like the inclusion of higher order thinking skills and the emphasis of affective and social elements makes the "fun way approach" something worth looking into.

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